

MERGE

MEASURING WHAT MATTERS

Policy pathways to sustainable and
inclusive wellbeing

Deliverable 6.1

Summary on EU and UN policy engagement

Version 1 | Date 23.06.2026

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Document History

Deliverable Title	Summary on EU and UN policy engagement
Brief Description	This report provides an overview on the events MERGE project organized at the EU and UN level that aimed to explore how a holistic set of metrics can enhance the design and monitor the implementation of policies. The report summarises the main insights, challenges and learnings gained through the process.
WP Number	WP6
Lead Beneficiary	ZOE institute for future fit economies
Author(s)	Laura Danilaviciute, Magali Brosio, Rachèle Chevallier
Deliverable Due Date	30/06/2026
Dissemination Level	Public
Keywords	Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing (SIW), UN, Metrics, Competitiveness, European Pillar of Social Rights, Intergenerational Fairness, European Semester, EU Budget, Clean Industrial Deal
License	CC BY
How to cite	Danilaviciute, L., Brosio, M. & Chevallier, R. (2026). Summary on EU and UN policy engagement. Merge project deliverable D6.1. Zenodo 10.5281/zenodo.20851296

Date	Ver.	Contributors	Comments
09/06/2026	0.1	Laura Danilaviciute, Rachele Chevallier, Magali Brosio (ZOE)	First draft
12/6/2026	0.2	Joseph Eastoe (UCL) Alisa Rannikko (TAU)	Internal review
23/6/2026	1.0	Laura Danilaviciute, Magali Brosio, Rachele Chevallier (ZOE)	Final version

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Acronyms used in the report

CID	Clean Industrial Deal
DNSH	Do-No-Significant-Harm
DG BUDG	Directorate-General for Budget
DG CLIMA	Directorate-General for Climate Action
DG ECFIN	Directorate-General for Economic and Financial Affairs
DG EMPL	Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion
DG ENER	Directorate-General for Energy
DG ENV	Directorate-General for Environment
DG ESTAT	Directorate-General for Statistics
DG GROW	Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs
DG MOVE	Directorate-General for Mobility and Transport
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
SG	Secretariat-General
EACEA	European Education and Culture Executive Agency
EGD	European Green Deal
EEA	European Environment Agency
EEB	European Environmental Bureau
EESC	European Economic and Social Committee
EPSR	European Pillar of Social Rights
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HLEG	United Nations High-Level Expert Group on Beyond GDP
JRC	Joint Research Centre
MFF	Multiannual Financial Framework
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SIW	Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing
JRC SIWB	JRC's Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing (dashboard)
UN	United Nations
US	United States

1. Introduction

Governments today face multidimensional challenges and demands: protecting against climate change, reducing poverty and inequality, providing quality jobs in a sustainable and resilient economy, improving health outcomes, and enhancing democratic participation. Building economies that truly deliver wellbeing for all - now and in the future - requires sophisticated policy tools and a holistic way of measuring progress. Metrics that capture multidimensional wellbeing outcomes and models that handle complexity, trade-offs, feedback loops, and long-term impacts can support complex this policy process. In this context, [MERGE, a Horizon Europe-funded project](#), aims to connect science and policy to develop indicators and models that can support sustainable and inclusive wellbeing policy processes within the multilevel governance.

This report covers European Union (EU) and United Nations (UN) policy engagement work under the policy section of the MERGE project, while other MERGE deliverables focus on different governance levels (national and regional)¹. The EU and UN level policy engagement work feeds into the further MERGE project development, such as the policy guidelines and online trainings for policy actors².

This report has four main sections. Firstly, we outline the engagement strategy for both the EU and UN levels for the integration of Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing as well as Beyond GDP approaches into policy. Secondly, we focus on the EU-level work, offering an overview of the main activities and key takeaways that emerged from them. We conclude the description of the EU level engagement with a summary of cross-cutting insights, challenges, limitations and learnings. Thirdly, we focus on the UN level engagement mirroring the structure above: overview of events (structured around two key workstreams), cross cutting insights, challenges, limitations and learnings. Lastly, the report concludes with some general reflections on the opportunities and challenges of embedding sustainable and inclusive wellbeing indicators into policy.

¹ Namely deliverable 6.2 and deliverable 5.

² Deliverable 8.1

2. Engagement strategy

While seeking to understand and explore the opportunities and challenges of the institutionalisation and mainstreaming of sustainable and inclusive wellbeing and Beyond GDP approaches³ through the policy and governance processes, the MERGE project engaged a broad ecosystem of EU-level as well as UN level actors. Both EU and UN-level engagement activities required the ability to adapt and respond to the changes in the external political environment, as well as to react to emerging opportunities and mitigate existing challenges.

The EU-level engagement was shaped by increased focus of political priorities of the 2024-2029 European institutions on competitiveness, decarbonisation, security and defence. This context limited institutional space and time for long-term, futures-oriented reflection. Therefore, engaging at the EU level through organising co-creative workshops that depend on participants' openness, continuity of engagement, and a diverse mix of expertise proved to be challenging: attendance was varied, discussions at times gravitated toward immediate concerns, and the conditions needed for deeper collective sense-making were often constrained. As a result, the insights gathered through these activities are necessarily partial and shaped by who was able and willing to participate under these circumstances. They should therefore be read with this limitation in mind, as reflections from a restricted window of engagement rather than a comprehensive picture of policy views across the EU institutions.

Similarly, the UN-level engagement was marked by multiple uncertainties regarding the post-Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) agenda. Although discussions on the future of this agenda are expected to take place during the 2027 SDG Summit (September 2027, New York City), multiple open questions still surround the process, making it hard to predict how these negotiations will unfold. The limited progress under the SDG framework (further complicated by the COVID-19 pandemic) and the UN financial crisis create a difficult environment for deepening some of the work started in 2015. More specifically, in connection to the Beyond GDP agenda, as Antonio Guterres's mandate ends in 2026, it is unclear to what extent this topic would be a priority for the future Secretary-General. All in all, while engaging in the preparatory work being carried out at this stage is crucial, the level of impact that it will have in the future direction of the UN is yet unclear.

³ For the EU level, a *sustainable and inclusive wellbeing* framing and, for the UN level, a *beyond GDP* framing were deliberately chosen after careful consideration of which language would be most suitable and resonant for stakeholders at each governance level.

The findings and reflections of the engagement activities are organised and presented through four analytical lenses: **insights, challenges, limitations and learnings**. They are presented in greater detail in the section 3.2 for the EU level and section 4.2 for the UN level.

Insights are the key observations that emerged from the events and analysis – new or sharpened understandings of how Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing (SIW) metrics interact with existing priorities, instruments and political dynamics.

Challenges are the observed obstacles that hinder the effective uptake of SIW metrics, including technical, political and institutional difficulties that policymakers encounter in practice.

Limitations refer to the deeper structural and contextual constraints – such as entrenched paradigms, governance arrangements and data gaps – that set boundaries on what can realistically be achieved and on how far the project's findings can be generalised.

Finally, **learnings** are the lessons drawn from the project's experiences, highlighting what has worked well, what has proved less effective, and how future efforts to embed SIW metrics in policies and processes can be strengthened.

2.1. EU-level engagement

Engagement at the EU level was structured around six **horizontal and sectoral policy areas**. These activities offered entry points for collaboration and science-policy as well as practical-technical exchange. Anchoring engagement in design-thinking and co-creative thinking methods opened avenues for open collaboration and innovative idea generation.

When developing the EU engagement, it was essential to ensure that the topics we focused on were closely aligned with the political priorities of the EU institutions at the time the events took place. To achieve this, we applied criteria for selecting areas of engagement: the topics needed to reflect current institutional priorities, address challenges actively debated by policy practitioners, and contain genuinely open questions where additional insights or co-creation could offer value. Following continuous monitoring of the 2024–2029 EU institutional agenda, supported by internal deliberation within the consortium, we identified six priority themes for the EU engagement activities under task 6.1 of the MERGE project. These were: **the EU Long-Term Budget or the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) post-2027; EU Competitiveness; the Clean Industrial Deal (CID); Social Europe; the European Semester; and EU Governance**. Together, these areas represented important

policy debates where MERGE had the potential to contribute meaningfully through evidence, dialogue, and forward-looking analysis.

The EU engagement activities were centred around these six policy areas, with a focus on specific policy proposals and horizontal policy areas. For each of the topics, we monitored the political landscape and discourse⁴, conducted targeted desk research⁵ and carried out informal conversations with partner organisations and policy practitioners to refine the political entry points.

Between February 2025 and February 2026, MERGE project policy partners organised 7 in-person workshops and 4 online science-policy dialogues. The workshops provided insights on how a holistic set of sustainable and inclusive wellbeing metrics - such as the [Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing Dashboard](#) created by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) - can enhance the design and monitoring of key EU policies in the six policy areas.

Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing (SIW) framework is composed of three interconnected dimensions (Costanza et al. 2024; Jansen et al, 2023):

- **“Wellbeing now”:** Ensuring a good life for all today. Includes key determinants of wellbeing, such as health, education, air quality, employment, social relationships, income, housing, security, environmental health, and peace.
- **“Wellbeing for all”:** Limiting inequalities across social groups. Gauges the distribution of wellbeing determinants and opportunities across spatial scales and social groups, such as gender inequality, income/wealth inequality, risk of poverty, child poverty and discrimination.
- **“Wellbeing in the future”:** Preserving conditions for future generations. Encompasses biophysical and social conditions for future wellbeing, including climate, biodiversity and other planetary boundaries, demographics and innovation capacity.

⁴ This was done by monitoring official EU institutions' websites, news outlets (Politico Pro, Euronews, EUObserver, Financial Times, etc), and relevant online seminars.

⁵ Desk research covered, among others, official EU communication documents and staff working documents, European Parliament's briefings, opinions from the European Court of Auditors, academic papers, and reports from NGOs, think tanks and unions.

[ZOE Institute for Future-fit Economies](#) accompanied by the [European Policy Centre \(EPC\)](#) and [Demos Helsinki](#) conducted the events.

Participants at these events included policy practitioners from different policy areas and different EU institutions as well as different hierarchy levels: European Commission (in DG RTD, JRC, DG BUDG, DG CLIMA, DG ENER, DG EMPL, DG ENV, DG ECFIN, DG ESTAT, DG GROW, DG MOVE, SG), European Parliament, European Committee of Regions, European Economic and Social Committee (EESC), Member States' Permanent Representations to the EU, experts in the field as well as representatives from the partner organisations (policy organisations, think tanks, university researchers) in the MERGE consortium and its sibling projects⁶. To support open discussion and collaboration among participants, the event was held under Chatham house rules⁷.

2.2. UN-level engagement

At the UN level, the engagement was organised around **two** key global processes that shaped discussions on sustainable and inclusive wellbeing throughout the MERGE project's lifespan (Jan 2024 – January 2027).⁸

The first was the mandate of [the High-Level Expert Group \(HLEG\) on Beyond GDP](#), appointed in May 2025 by the UN Secretary-General to identify a concise set of indicators for assessing societal progress. The process formally started with the Pact for the Future (adopted in September 2024) and had a major milestone in May 2026, with the publication of the report 'Counting what Counts' (United Nations, 2026).

The second process, called **Eradicating poverty beyond growth**, was led by the former UN Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights, Olivier De Schutter. In July 2024,

⁶ See more information on the MERGE consortium and its sibling projects at <https://mergeproject.eu/>

⁷ When a meeting, or part thereof, is held under the Chatham House Rule, participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed. from <https://www.chathamhouse.org/about-us/chatham-house-rule>

⁸ During this period, a third relevant workstream emerged: the Beyond GDP Global Alliance, co-led by Spain, Uruguay, and Senegal, with the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), UN Trade and Development (UNCTAD), and the Ibero-American General Secretariat (SEGIB). While the group was launched at the Fourth International Conference on Financing for Development, it only entered its operational phase in April 2026. While the MERGE consortium members have been interacting with the organising partners – through bilateral meetings, but also organising a session at the 7th OECD World Forum on Wellbeing – there were no open consultations for external stakeholders during this period. Hence, while recognising the importance of this process, most of the consortium efforts during this period were devoted to the two processes described in this deliverable.

the Special Rapporteur presented his report ‘Eradicating poverty beyond growth’ to the Human Rights Council, showcasing the need to move away from growth-dependent development strategies and towards a human rights economy (De Schutter, 2024). After this report, the Special Rapporteur started working – together with multiple stakeholders – on a supplementary material that could provide concrete guidance on how to implement this vision: the Roadmap for Eradicating Poverty Beyond Growth was developed and presented in Geneva in April 2026⁹.

Across both processes, the MERGE consortium contributed through a range of activities: submitting input to open consultations, delivering presentations upon request, holding bilateral exchanges with members of the respective teams, and convening regular consortium-wide meetings with participants engaged in these UN-level processes to ensure alignment between the project’s work and ongoing international developments.

While the actual impact of these two processes remains unknown at the time of writing this report, both aim to shape the discussions around the framework that will replace the UN Agenda 2030 and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

3. EU level engagement: Overview and main takeaways

This section provides an overview of the EU-level engagement activities. First, it outlines a series of events carried out as part of our engagement strategy. Then, it provides a summary of the insights, learnings, challenges, and limitations we have identified across them.

3.1. EU-level engagement: Overview of events

At the EU level, the 11 workshops and events were delivered through a variety of interactive formats, drawing on design-thinking principles and co-creative methods. This included facilitated interactive discussions such as World Café sessions, expert inputs, guided questions, and small-group dialogues. Participants received preparatory briefing papers, and the sessions were supported by presentation materials used during the workshops.

⁹ The Roadmap will be officially presented to the 62nd session of the UN Human Rights Council on 25th June, 2026. The Roadmap was adopted in April 2026 at the International Labour Organization (ILO) in Geneva at a major international convening organised under the mandate of the UN Special Rapporteur and the auspices of the ILO’s Global Coalition for Social Justice.

After each event, summary documents captured the main insights and key takeaways from the discussions and were shared with participants. This also facilitated follow-up engagement.

After the events follow-up conversations were conducted with participants and other stakeholders. These discussions fed into the formulation of the key takeaways as well as learnings, insights and challenges of using a holistic set of metrics to enhance and monitor the implementation of key EU policies.

The next section provides a more detailed overview of the events, giving details on time, location, participants and main takeaways.

3.1.1. Workshop: “Measuring what matters: Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing metrics in the EU Budget”

Time: February 4th, 2025, 9-11 am

Location: Joint Research Centre Policy Lab CDMA Building,

Overview: During the workshop, participants jointly explored the challenges and opportunities of integrating SIW metrics into the [new Multiannual Financial Framework](#) and its monitoring framework. Applying the SIW lens helped explore how to ensure that long-term investments and budgetary priorities directly support people’s quality of life, reduce inequalities, and remain within environmental limits. The focus was placed on two concrete entry points: performance-based budgeting and the do-no-significant-harm (DNSH) principle. The advancement of the performance-based principle and the embedding of the DNSH principle within the EU budget represent an important opportunity for ensuring accountability in the use of EU funds. It also can create initiatives for EU Member States to adhere to the EU goals.

Participants: EU institutions such as the European Commission, the European Parliament, the Committee of Regions, the EESC, trade unions, EU Member States’ Permanent Representations, and MERGE partners.

Key takeaways:

- **A need for clear definitions and shared understanding of SIW metrics.** Improved definitions, scope, and structure of SIW metrics so that all stakeholders have a consistent understanding of what is being measured. This can facilitate the meaningful integration of SIW into policy processes.
- **A need to have metrics that are actionable.** Actionable metrics can provide actionable insights and incentives for positive policy outcomes. The selection of SIW metrics needs to ensure that they do not create unnecessary complexity.
- **When metrics are embedded in governance structures political barriers are lower.** Integrating SIW indicators formally into regulations and governance structures is essential for overcoming political barriers and preventing their dilution or de-prioritisation over time.
- **MFF as an avenue for SIW approach.** MFF and its performance framework as one of the major initiatives presents an important avenue for SIW approach.

3.1.2 Workshop: “Measuring what matters: Sustainable and Inclusive wellbeing metrics in the Clean Industrial Deal (CID)”

Time: March 26th, 2025, 9:30-11:30 am

Location: Joint Research Centre Policy Lab CDMA Building

Overview: The workshop aimed to discuss how sustainable and inclusive wellbeing indicators can help ensure that the [Clean Industrial Deal](#) (CID) aligns with the [European Green Deal](#) (EGD)’s environmental and social objectives, enabling a just and green transition, as well as fostering sustainable prosperity and wellbeing for all, now and in the future. Applying sustainable and inclusive wellbeing metrics to the CID offers an approach for aligning industrial transformation with social fairness and health, ensuring that decarbonisation pathways enhance rather than undermine people’s wellbeing.

Participants from EU institutions, along with experts in the field, reflected on questions such as “How can socio-ecological and wellbeing dimensions be better integrated into the EGD and CID frameworks to ensure a just and inclusive transition?” and “How can we streamline the EGD and CID frameworks for monitoring and addressing data gaps?”

Participants: EU institutions such as the European Commission, the European Parliament, Member States' Permanent Representations, and MERGE partners.

Key takeaways:

- **Data gaps.** Incorporating SIW indicators into the European Green Deal and Clean Industrial Deal presents both challenges and opportunities. Managing the risk of increasing reporting burdens, leveraging existing datasets, exploring new data sources, and improving integration processes can help fill these gaps.
- **People centred approaches.** By identifying entry points for SIW indicators and focusing on people-centred approaches, monitoring frameworks can work together to provide a holistic view of the green transition.
- **Benefits of SIW integration in policies.** SIW integration can support evidence-based narratives, ensure social inclusivity, and enhance public support for a just and sustainable transition.

3.1.3 Workshop: “Measuring what matters: Competitiveness”

Time: May 23rd, 2025, 9:30-11:30 am

Location: Joint Research Centre Policy Lab CDMA Building,

Overview: The discussion centred on how competitiveness – a flagship priority of the 2024-2029 mandate – can be defined and measured to reflect long-term sustainability. Assessing EU competitiveness through a SIW lens offered an opportunity to reframe progress beyond cost and productivity alone, focusing on innovation, human capabilities, social cohesion, and environmental resilience as core drivers of long-term competitiveness.

To explore this, participants analysed two specific policy examples that are part of the EU's competitiveness agenda: the [Circular Economy Act](#) and [Quality Jobs Roadmap](#) initiatives. This helped to narrow down the scope of the otherwise broad topic. The two examples were indicated as potential entry points to explore possibilities for integrating the SIW lens into competitiveness.

A recurring theme in the discussion was the need for policy tools, under the competitiveness umbrella, that assist with managing the potential trade-offs between environmental outcomes, social objectives and economic performance. The EU's future competitiveness lies not just in economic output, but in its ability to foster a resilient, fair, and green society.

Embedding these principles in definitions, measurements, policy instruments and governance frameworks is critical for achieving a sustainable and inclusive European model.

Participants: EU institutions such as the European Commission, EU Member States Permanent Representations, MERGE partners, and experts in the field.

Key takeaways:

- **Broader definition and framing of competitiveness are needed.** The current framing of economic competitiveness centres around short-term productivity and growth. This does not reflect today's complex social and environmental realities, such as resource scarcity, climate and supply-chain risks, and social cohesion challenges, to name just a few. Framing competitiveness for long-term sustainability extends beyond economic performance. Wider definitions include environmental sustainability, social inclusion and wellbeing, institutional and economic resilience. This allows us to acknowledge that long-term prosperity hinges on a society's capacity to innovate, adapt, and thrive within ecological and social boundaries. However, the challenge of balancing environmental and social goals with economic ones persists. Particularly considering the need of industry adaptation and job retention within the EU.
- **Considering the broader framing when selecting measurement tools for competitiveness can be helpful.** Sustainability and inclusiveness need to be central to the EU's long-term competitiveness agenda. Policy coherence across social, environmental, and economic domains is important for fostering inclusive prosperity.
- **Two entry points are important to consider. Circular economy Act and Quality Jobs Roadmap.** **Circular Economy Act** serves as an entry point. Adopting **resource productivity as a key aspect of competitiveness** can support building the circular economy as a strategic sector of the EU, which is competitive, resilient and ensures strategic autonomy. For the **Quality Jobs Roadmap**, another strong pillar of Competitiveness agenda, participants indicated the need for more **comprehensive employment indicators** that can capture job security, fair wages, mental health, and diversity of employment types. It is important to recognise informal and unpaid labour (e.g. care work) in policy frameworks to avoid exclusion and support equitable participation in the labour market.

3.1.4 Workshop: “Measuring what matters: Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing metrics in the European Pillar of Social Rights (EPSR)”

Time: June 3rd, 2025. 9:30-11:30 am

Location: Joint Research Centre Policy Lab CDMA Building,

Overview: In the context of the upcoming EPSR Action Plan review, this workshop brought together EU policymakers and experts to discuss how the EPSR can promote sustainable and inclusive wellbeing, and how SIW indicators can be better integrated into monitoring frameworks such as the Social Scoreboard¹⁰. Viewing the [European Pillar of Social Rights](#) (EPSR) through sustainable and inclusive wellbeing metrics highlighted whether social rights are effectively translating into tangible improvements in people's lives, especially for those most at risk of exclusion. Participants discussed which measures should be included in the upcoming revision of the EPSR Action Plan to advance SIW, and how to further improve its monitoring framework, the Social Scoreboard.

Participants: The European Commission, the European Parliament, Member States' Permanent Representations to the EU, trade unions, MERGE partners and experts in the field.

Key takeaways:

- **Aligning Social Rights with the EU's Strategic priorities.** The EPSR could connect to the current political narrative alongside priorities such as competitiveness, security, and the green and digital transitions. This requires aligning social rights with the Union's evolving agenda without diluting their purpose. However, the EPSR's original role can serve as a counternarrative to agendas sidelining social rights amid rising competitiveness and security, and can be framed not just as a social add-on but as a driver of resilience, legitimacy, and prosperity.
- **Challenge: Political prioritisation.** Social rights are often sidelined in favour of more urgent-seeming economic or geopolitical concerns. Repositioning the EPSR demands high-level political ownership, narrative coherence, and cross-sectoral buy-in across EU institutions and member states.
- **Strengthening the Scoreboard's reliability, granularity and policy relevance.** The Social Scoreboard must evolve into a more comprehensive and responsive tool that reflects the full scope of social realities across Member States. This means addressing current limitations such as delayed, inconsistent, and incomplete data, while ensuring that indicators capture not only income levels but also lived experiences, inequalities,

¹⁰ For the revised Social Scoreboard please see the Social Pillar Action Plan: <https://op.europa.eu/webpub/empl/european-pillar-of-social-rights/en/#annex2>

and access to rights. When used alongside macroeconomic governance tools, the Scoreboard can support timely, targeted policymaking.

- **Challenge: Data and design limitations.** The current Scoreboard suffers from outdated indicators, irregular updates, and significant coverage gaps (e.g. housing exclusion, job quality, adult learning). Many indicators lack granularity and fail to reflect the diversity of social challenges across the EU. A fairer Scoreboard requires political will, investment in new data sources, methodological transparency, and a shift toward more contextual and disaggregated metrics.

3.1.5 Workshop: “Measuring Intergenerational Fairness: Indicators for Future-fit Governance in the EU”

Time: October 21st, 2025, 9:30-11:30 am

Location: Joint Research Centre Policy Lab CDMA Building,

Overview: SIW lens on the EU long-term governance highlighted institutional capacity to consider intergenerational impacts, manage systemic risks, and keep long-term societal resilience at the centre of decision-making. In the context of the development of the [EU Strategy for Intergenerational Fairness](#) at that time, participants explored how to translate “future wellbeing” into actionable indicators. The insights from the discussion aimed to inform progress toward long-term governance and notably the Strategy for Intergenerational Fairness, and the design of its monitoring framework and potential index. Participants were invited to explore how SIW metrics can help the EU understand the long-term impacts of today’s decisions, so that they ensure the wellbeing of current and future generations, for example by helping anticipate future trajectories and detecting emerging risks and opportunities.

Participants: European Commission, EESC, EACEA, OECD, MERGE partners.

Key takeaways

- Monitoring intergenerational fairness requires **diverse, forward-looking and systemic long-term governance indicators:** Emphasis was placed on capturing trajectories, early-warning signals, and societal capacities (e.g., social connectedness, civic engagement, time-use patterns) to inform proactive governance.

- **Clarifying what success looks like**, and setting actionable common targets, along with indicators that can demonstrate clear policy impact, is critical for prioritising the SIW indicators most useful for long-term governance.
- Better understanding **social connectedness** is central for intergenerational fairness as well as more broadly for the health of our societies. However, current data collection efforts (e.g. surveys on loneliness, people's participation in activities and volunteering) remain done infrequently or at an ad-hoc basis.
- **Social cohesion, intergenerational relations and transmission**, as well as trust, were identified as critical, yet under-monitored drivers of future wellbeing and societal resilience. Innovation in data collection and integration of data into a monitoring framework is crucial for guiding long-term social policy.

3.1.6 Workshop: “Towards a European Semester that promotes wellbeing in the medium-long term?”

Time: November 17th, 2025, 9:30-11:30 am

Location: EPC- in person and online on zoom platform.

Overview: Looking at the European Semester through a SIW lens offered an opportunity to discuss how economic and fiscal coordination can be guided by broader societal outcomes, better balancing macroeconomic stability with social, environmental, and intergenerational goals. The workshop focused on opportunities and challenges of broadening the [European Semester](#), in the medium-long term, to better integrate SIW dimensions and metrics. Participants were invited to work on case studies based on selected 2025 Country Specific Recommendations (CSRs) with thematic focus on housing and skills (social dimension) and on energy and green (transition) skills (sustainability), exploring how recommendations could look like if SIW dimensions were reinforced and which SIW indicators could be used.

Participants: European Commission, EESC, EEA, European Parliament, one Permanent Representation, MERGE partners.

Key takeaways:

- **The SIW framework is broadly complementary to the SDGs and could support a more holistic European Semester, but meaningful integration is unlikely in the short-term.** The following proposals for such integration were identified: add a dedicated SIW reporting component similar to the reporting on progress towards SDGs, develop a more holistic reporting of productivity to include SIW

dimensions, continue the discussions in the European Commission's Greening the Semester expert group and use the Eighth Environment Action Programme to further investigate the links between the European Semester and the work on beyond GDP.

- **Stronger monitoring requires clearer indicator use, but data gaps remain.** The JRC Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing (JRC SIWB) dashboard is seen as a useful entry point to flag risks and missing indicators rather than a detailed assessment tool. The existence of a common dashboard should serve to compare and assess the gravity of challenges across different areas in the same country (e.g. housing versus skills). Moreover, having a common dashboard such as the SIW framework would be very useful to see which countries are doing better in very specific areas and which are not; in terms of impact assessment, such a dashboard could identify those areas where a policy may have an impact and side effects, to develop a more standardised approach to policymaking.
- **Concerns about the ad-hoc nature of many Country Specific Recommendations were raised especially in the housing field.** Housing also emerged as one of the areas with the most acute indicator gaps. It is not clear why some countries receive very detailed recommendations despite relatively better housing outcomes, while others with severe shortages of affordable or social housing receive little or no attention. A common, transparent dashboard could help rank housing challenges across Member States, assess their relative severity, and support a more consistent and holistic approach to policymaking. In energy and the environmental field, the main challenge seems to lie in CSRs' implementation by Member States.

3.1.7 Policy Lab “Measuring What Matters: Governance for the Long Game. Mainstreaming sustainable and inclusive wellbeing metrics in EU governance”

Time: November 24th, 2025. 9:30-11:30 am

Location: Joint Research Centre Policy Lab CDMA Building,

Overview: The Policy lab was a concluding event that aimed to summarise and build on the discussions of the deep dive workshops. It built on the questions centring previous workshops such as the following: What are the alternative tools to assess progress? How

can MERGE research findings potentially facilitate the practical adoption of such tools, to support the implementation and monitoring of EU policies?

One of the strongly recurring themes that emerged during the six deep dive workshops was **the importance of setting strong outcome and result indicators to track progress and achieving wide policy goals**. We therefore explored this topic in greater depth in the policy lab format. During the group discussion, participants were invited to examine the barriers and opportunities for **using the JRC SIWB Dashboard and its indicators as a potential foundation** for developing outcome and result indicators for the wider EU goals in different policy areas.

Participants: European Commission, European Parliament, MERGE partners.

Key takeaways:

- **Competitiveness, sustainability, and wellbeing are interconnected and indicators that reflect this integrated approach can be helpful.** Discussion emphasised that the issue is no longer a lack of frameworks but rather how to operationalise them within EU governance. SIW indicators can serve as outcome measures in concrete processes such as budgeting, the European Semester, and policy evaluation.
- **Indicators need to balance complexity, usability, and narrative.** Building on prior discussions about metrics, participants stressed that effective indicators must be structured, tiered, and communicable to serve experts, policymakers, and citizens simultaneously. Crucially, indicators need to tell a clear story about progress, competitiveness, and transition, including the cost of inaction, rather than function as purely technical tools. Although simplicity, clarity, and narrative help political uptake and citizen communication, complexity must be managed. Tools need tiers: technical for experts, strategic for policymakers, and understandable for citizens.
- **Wellbeing, competitiveness, and sustainability are inseparable in practice.** Reinforcing insights from the deep dive workshops, the lab highlighted that these three agendas are not competing but mutually reinforcing. **The key challenge is political:** aligning wellbeing and sustainability within current priorities (e.g. security, competitiveness) and demonstrating their relevance through tangible benefits, local action, and citizen engagement, thereby strengthening legitimacy and uptake. Indicators that show direction (transition), outcomes, and bottlenecks- are more helpful for policy makers.
- **Efforts to decouple economic growth from emissions have been incomplete and green transition policies have had social costs** (e.g., job losses, instability, inequality).

The United Nations' Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Changes warns of the risk of "transition by disaster" if social fairness is neglected while designing policies.

3.1.8 Science-policy dialogue: "Measuring what matters - Economy that Would Improve Wellbeing for All Now and in the Future"

Time: 3rd of February 2025, 3 PM CET.

Location: Online Zoom Platform

Overview: This policy-focused event aimed to **disseminate MERGE project results** to a broad audience, including policymakers, researchers, advisors, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and think tanks, while addressing the growing need to rethink how prosperity is defined and measured in Europe. Against a backdrop of geopolitical instability, climate crises, rising living costs, and increasing political polarisation, the event highlighted the limitations of GDP as the dominant indicator of progress and called for a shift toward frameworks that better capture **sustainable and inclusive wellbeing**. It emphasised the urgency of coordinated action and the role of improved data and metrics in shaping future-oriented economic policies. It featured contributions from leading researchers and practitioners spanning national and EU-level perspectives, including Tuuli Hirvilammi (Tampere University), Rutger Hoekstra (Leiden University), Robert Costanza (University College London), and Dennis Snower (Global Solutions Initiative). The event focused on how separated streams of beyond-GDP work like doughnut economics, wellbeing economies, post-growth, degrowth, can converge into an integrated system of goals, metrics, models, and policies oriented toward SIW. It built on MERGE's consolidation of around 90 beyond-GDP metrics and aimed to connect academic insights with concrete policy action, particularly in the context of positioning the EU to lead and set standards for an economy that prioritises wellbeing for people and planet.

Participants: 334 people registered to the event, from civil society, NGOs, academia, private sector, business associations, national statistical institutes, think tanks, international organisations (OECD, EEA, UN), MERGE partners, and European Commission as well as national and regional representatives.

Key takeaways

- **The demand for a beyond-GDP economy is real and the challenge is delivery.** MERGE survey of European citizens, noted that over 80% of respondents support including beyond-GDP measures in national progress assessments, and 72% agree the economy should prioritise the health and wellbeing of people and nature over profit alone.
- **The fragmented beyond-GDP landscape is already converging,** but it needs to merge into a single, integrated system. In analysing around 90 beyond-GDP metrics, MERGE researchers identified convergence points at the indicator, thematic, and conceptual levels.
- **Wellbeing can be measured as both an individual and a collective construct,** consistently across countries and over time.

3.1.9 Science-Policy dialogue: “Measuring what matters. Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing metrics in the EU Budget”

Time: April 29th, 2025, 09:30-11:30 CET

Location: Online Zoom platform

Overview: The event showcased examples from national (well-being framework and the whole-of-year budgetary process in Ireland) and international level (OECD wellbeing evidence in budgetary process) where wellbeing budgeting has been implemented.

The event focused on how multidimensional wellbeing metrics can inform EU budgetary and investment policies. It built on MERGE’s policy deep dive on the EU Budget and aimed to connect academic insights with practical policy applications, particularly in the context of shaping EU funding priorities.

Participants: European Commission, National government experts, OECD, European Parliament, European Committee of the Regions, MERGE partners.

Key takeaways

- **Wellbeing budgeting is about transforming policymaking, not adding indicators.** Frameworks shape priorities, trade-offs, and investment decisions across government, rather than sitting beside traditional budgets as a decorative dashboard.

- **There is no single ‘wellbeing budget’ model – diversity of practice is the reality.** Countries use different combinations of dashboards, priority-setting, budget tagging, and impact assessments (e.g. New Zealand, Ireland, Italy, Iceland, Bhutan), and this experimentation is a strength for learning.
- **Principle of wellbeing is more than the label of ‘wellbeing’.** The shared core is a multidimensional, people-focused, equity-oriented, long-term outcomes approach. In some contexts (like the EU), it may be more pragmatic to talk about “multidimensional, outcomes-based decision-making” than to foreground the word “wellbeing”.
- **Linking wellbeing to competitiveness** and value for money requires building solid methods to show how social and wellbeing investments improve productivity and long-term competitiveness. This is important when communicating with finance sector and fitting into existing budget cultures (e.g. MFF, “budget for results”).

3.1.10 Science-policy dialogue: “Competitiveness: measuring what matters”

Time: February 29th, 2026, 9:30-11:30 am

Location: Online Zoom platform

Overview: The event was organised as a follow up to the Competitiveness deep dive workshop and built on the discussions of the defining and measuring competitiveness. It focused on rethinking how the European Union approaches competitiveness by integrating long-term sustainability, wellbeing, and social cohesion. It brought together researchers, policymakers, business leaders, and civil society.

Through expert presentations, commentary, and discussion, the dialogue explored whether current EU competitiveness frameworks are compatible with sustainability and wellbeing goals, what dimensions a future-fit model should include, and how such approaches can be embedded in governance processes. By linking conceptual debates with practical policymaking realities, the event explored a shift from narrow measures of economic performance toward a more holistic understanding of prosperity that balances economic, social, and environmental objectives.

Participants: 150 people registered to the event, from civil society, NGOs, academia, private sector, business associations, national statistical institutes, think tanks, international organisations (OECD, EEB, EEA, UN), MERGE partners, and European Commission.

Key takeaways

- **Economic indicators alone miss key aspects of quality of life, distribution, and environmental sustainability;** the EU’s treaty mandate point to well-being as the overarching goal.
- **Comparison data show the EU and US differ when comparing economic versus wellbeing, equality and sustainability metrics.** While the EU lags on income and labour productivity, it has broadly caught up or overtaken the US on life satisfaction, human development, distribution of income/wealth, safety, and environmental performance-especially when looking beyond averages and address inequalities.
- **New metrics and methods can reshape the competitiveness narrative.** Interdisciplinary wellbeing frameworks and advanced measures (e.g. combining income, lifespan, and inequality) provide a richer picture of welfare than GDP per capita, and can change EU–US “who is better off” rankings once inequality and non-monetary dimensions are factored in.
- **Circular economy (and regenerative models), social investment, climate and health impacts as well as the cost of inaction** are powerful entry points to illustrate that protecting people and the planet reduces long-run economic risks and can underpin a more future-fit, competitive European model.

3.1.11 Science-policy dialogue: “Towards a Prosperous Europe – Shaping Policies for Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing”

Time: October 30th, 2025, 15-16:30 CET

Location: Online Zoom platform

Overview: The event showcased examples from MERGE research, including a shortlist of 19 scrutinised policy instruments across five themes (access to social services, labour policies, economic transformation, environment, and democracy) and the consolidation of hundreds of beyond-GDP indicators into a shared 20-component conceptual backbone. The event focused on how to find convergence across policy measures and identify the political drivers for a transition towards sustainable and inclusive wellbeing. It built on

MERGE's policy deep dives and engagement with EU policymakers and aimed to connect academic insights with practical policy applications, particularly in the context of aligning EU governance tools such as the Competitiveness Compass and the upcoming Multiannual Financial Framework with wellbeing goals.

Participants: 144 people registered to the event, from civil society, NGOs, academia, private sector, business associations, national statistical institutes, think tanks, international organisations (OECD, EEA, UN), MERGE partners, and European Commission as well as national and regional representatives.

Key takeaways

- **There is no lack of potential policies supporting SIW**, ranging from Universal basic income to granting rights to nature. MERGE has compiled a list of 19 policy instruments, spanning five themes: access to social services, labour policies, economic transformation, environment, and democracy. Even though the listed policies show promise, many would benefit from further piloting and impact evaluation.
- **Engagement work with EU policymakers on integrating SIW metrics into governance and monitoring frameworks revealed a clear shift: from simply developing new indicators toward adopting a long-term, integrated approach that breaks silos and cuts across all policy areas.** Policymakers emphasised that they do not need more data, but rather actionable insights that connect with political priorities.
- **MERGE analysis highlights a consensus among hundreds of beyond-GDP indicators:** despite methodological and cultural differences, most wellbeing indicators share a common conceptual backbone, condensed into 20 components. The question is not what to measure, but how to measure, and which policies and models support the measurement.

3.2 Reflections – EU level

This section of the report captures reflections and summarises what was observed (insights), what was difficult (challenges), what constrained the work (limitations), and what can be taken forward (learnings) while aiming to look for opportunities to integrate SIW approach into policy making.

3.2.1 Insights

Shift in policy paradigm: There is growing recognition amongst participants of the events that for EU policy to move towards sustainable and inclusive wellbeing supported by SIW metrics, there is a need for a change in the policy paradigm. This is especially true in areas such as the EU budget, competitiveness, and social policy. At the same time, European priorities have been shifting away from longer-term objectives (e.g. biodiversity protection, just transition) towards more immediate needs and short-term priorities, such as defence, security and competitiveness. In addition, the focus on simplification of the second von der Leyen Commission also means less opportunities for new metrics and monitoring tools. This

change of political context was evident in the discussions and also impacted the willingness of policy makers to discuss these topics openly. Therefore, the active participation of policymakers in the MERGE event required time and personal-level communication to create a safe and trusted environment for policy practitioners to exchange. Overall, this indicates that embedding SIW metrics depends as much on political timing and framing as on technical design.

Integrating metrics into policy tools: Conditionality or performance-based budgeting, DNSH principle, and monitoring frameworks (e.g., Social Scoreboard, CID, EGD) emerged as concrete entry points where SIW metrics can be potentially embedded into EU policymaking. These instruments offer practical channels to make wellbeing considerations visible in budgetary, regulatory and monitoring processes, provided they can accommodate a broader set of indicators. Analysing these policy tools through the SIW lens can offer a potential to highlight gaps.

Cross-pillar relevance: SIW metrics are not sector-specific; they cut across environmental, social, and economic dimensions, making them relevant for broader challenges and political priorities such as competitiveness, cohesion, social rights, and industrial strategy. Compiled into a monitoring framework, as in the European Commission Joint Research Centre's Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing dashboard, they offer an overarching view that can facilitate the coherence and people-centricity of the political narrative and the coordination of policies across dimensions. At the same time, policymakers following thematic files, will continue to need more specific indicators for each policy area to keep delivery focus, accountability and ability to adjust in real time. Nevertheless, a SIW approach can support adopting a wider perspective even on more specific topics. Thus, SIW dashboards that prioritise clarity and focus are more likely to be used in real political decision-making.

From complexity to usability: Policymakers operate in a complex, fast-moving environment and need straightforward, simple, “decision-ready” and actionable tools. The usability of dashboards depends on how easy, intuitive and focused they are. When well designed, such tools help to keep policy anchored in evidence, even if political attention shifts away from high sustainability ambition. This highlights that the perceived usefulness of SIW metrics is closely linked to their presentation and usability.

Building political and institutional buy-in: The challenge is less about inventing new indicators and more about ensuring **uptake and consistency across EU policy areas**. Showcasing successful examples of use of SIW metrics, e.g. in wellbeing budgeting, and linking SIW metrics to citizens' everyday concerns (e.g., jobs, childcare, inequalities, and security) can strengthen political legitimacy. These strategies offer a pathway to build cross-

party support. In turn, this can help shift SIW metrics from being seen as a niche, technical agenda towards a strong element of the EU's long-term competitiveness and social model.

3.2.2 Challenges

Complexity and trade-offs: Policymakers struggle to balance social, environmental, and economic objectives in a context of frequent crises and short-term pressures. Currently, competitiveness and wellbeing policies are not sufficiently integrated, and short-term feasibility often dominates over longer-term considerations. This weakens the space for SIW metrics to inform strategic choices.

Indicators and data gaps: While there is consensus on the need for holistic set of indicators, there are gaps in reliable and more granular data, especially for measuring outcomes limiting the robustness and usability of SIW-based assessments in policies.

Communication and usability: Decision makers have limited time and attention. The effective use of SIW metrics therefore depends on the capacity to translate technical information into concise, visual, and decision-friendly formats (e.g. dashboards, scoreboards, spotlighting practical examples). When this translation is missing, SIW metrics risk remaining underused, even when data exist.

Consistency across frameworks: Different EU frameworks (MFF, competitiveness, EPSR, social scoreboard, CID/EGD) risk fragmentation if wellbeing metrics are introduced unevenly, rather than through a coherent EU-wide approach. Without a more coherent EU-wide approach, SIW metrics may contribute to complexity rather than improving alignment across policy domains.

Shifting political focus: The increasing calls for simplification and reducing the data collection burden were identified as challenges for developing and improving SIW metrics.

3.2.3 Limitations

A key cross-cutting structural limitation is that the shift to SIW measurements and policymaking requires a broader paradigm change. This extends beyond data and indicators to change in incentives, institutions, communication practices, political culture, and public expectations. A related limitation is linked to the way the broader policy process uses metrics: metrics alone cannot be treated as a solution. A more holistic approach to policy

design is needed, one that systematically integrates social, environmental, and governance dimensions beyond data.

Whereas the previous subsection focused on immediate, practical challenges, the limitations below concern deeper, structural features of the EU policy system that constrain the uptake of SIW metrics.

The remaining limitations are split into 4 types; Systemic, Political and Strategic, Communicability and Utility, and Governance and Institutional limitations.

Systemic limitations

- **Fragmented policy instruments:** sustainability, competitiveness, and social wellbeing are treated as separate policy domains, though reality is overlapping. The governance fragmentation reinforces this structural separation.
- **Limited tools to show the “cost of inaction”:** There is a lack of mechanisms and macroeconomic analyses that quantify the positive and negative impacts of sectoral policies on other relevant policy areas, including the costs of delayed transitions. This reduces the visibility of the long-term benefits of SIW-oriented policies and the risks of maintaining the status quo.
Political buy-in and institutional resistance: Integrating SIW metrics requires shifting entrenched approaches (GDP focus, siloed, governance, short-term vs. long-term policymaking). Institutional inertia and political sensitivity may slow uptake.

Political and strategic limitations

- **Targets as political symbolism:** Targets can serve more as political signals than as steering instruments for policymaking, limiting their effectiveness in driving concrete changes aligned with SIW objectives.
- **Short-termism vs. transitions:** Long-term transitions necessary for sustainable and inclusive wellbeing often conflict with short-term policy cycles and crisis responses. This structural tension constrains the consistent use of SIW metrics in strategic decision-making.

Communication limitations

- **Complexity vs. simplicity trade-off:** Meaningful wellbeing indicators are complex, but political and citizen messaging demands simplicity. Moreover, existing

institutional set-ups and processes as well as communication channels and their siloed design structure cannot easily translate complex wellbeing evidence into tailored tools that serve different policy areas or audiences.

- **Multiple audiences and different needs:** Internal management, high-level policy steering, and public communication require different types of information and levels of detail. A single tool cannot easily serve all these purposes simultaneously, and current arrangements often lack the capacity and resources to maintain differentiated yet coherent SIW tools across audiences.

Governance and institutional limitations

- **Multi-level complexity:** Alignment across the EU, national, and regional levels, is weak. Differences in data availability, administrative capacity and political priorities make it difficult to embed SIW metrics consistently throughout the different levels of government.
- **Siloed ownership:** Policy areas operate with their own measurement cultures, mandates, budgets and incentives. This siloed ownership of indicators and dashboards makes it harder to introduce cross-cutting SIW metrics and to sustain joint responsibility for their use.

3.2.4 Learnings

Policy uptake improves with concrete examples: Case studies of wellbeing budgeting (national and international) helped make the concept tangible for policymakers. This improved dialogue and interest. Future efforts should prioritise piloting and documenting specific SIW use cases (e.g. wellbeing budgeting) to support uptake.

Applying a multi-dimensional lens to policy can be a successful framing for policymakers: Various workshops, such as the competitiveness workshop or the EU Semester workshop showed momentum towards a broader framing, where resilience, fairness, and sustainability are part of Europe's long-term competitiveness model, not just economic performance.

Science-policy dialogue works: Structured discussions between researchers and policymakers created a shared language and helped bridge gaps between technical metrics and political priorities. Intentional stakeholder grouping formats allowed active involvement from both sides and were successful in enabling discussions at the events or participating

in the open calls for consultations. Maintaining regular, structured dialogue formats should be part of the institutionalisation of SIW metrics.

Opportunities for alignment: The EPSR review, MFF post-2027 performance framework, were identified as most promising windows of opportunity to embed SIW metrics into major EU processes. Strategically, this indicates, that by connecting SIW metrics to existing governance instruments and reform debates can help move from experimental use to more systematic integration.

4. UN policy engagement: Overview and main takeaways

This section provides an overview of the UN level engagement activities. First, it explains how the MERGE consortium engaged with two workstreams. Then, the next sub-section, provides a summary of the insights, challenges, limitations and learnings we have identified across them.

4.1. UN level engagement: Overview of the activities

The international agenda on Beyond GDP has gained significant momentum in recent years. Under the leadership of UN Secretary-general António Guterres, this work has moved to the forefront, with several important processes emerging. Within this context, UN-level engagement during the MERGE project centred on two key global initiatives that shaped discussions on sustainable and inclusive wellbeing.¹¹

The first was the High-Level Expert Group on Beyond GDP, appointed by the UN Secretary-General and tasked with identifying a concise set of indicators to assess societal progress. The second was the Roadmap for Eradicating Poverty Beyond Growth, led by the Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights, Olivier De Schutter.

¹¹ In addition to the concrete activities mentioned in this section, MERGE has established an international level working group, that includes not only consortium members, but also external participants involved with all relevant process (namely, the Roadmap, HLEG, and the Global Alliance). The group has met regularly throughout the project lifespan to share relevant updates, including opportunities to engage and align.

Across both processes, the MERGE consortium contributed through a wide range of activities. In the following pages, we outline how we engaged with each initiative. For each, we provide background information, an overview of our contributions, and key takeaways.

4.1.1 High-Level Expert Group on Beyond GDP

Background of the process: In the 2021 report, Our Common Agenda, and the follow-up policy brief on Beyond GDP, the UN Secretary General António Guterres reaffirmed the need for moving beyond GDP (United Nations, 2021, 2023). In September 2024, UN Member States committed to the Pact for the Future to develop “a framework on measures of progress on sustainable development to complement and go beyond gross domestic product” (United Nations General Assembly, 2024). A High-Level Expert Group (HLEG) was set up in May 2025, with the mission to propose a set of 10 to 20 headline indicators to facilitate the global coordinated move towards beyond GDP measurement. These recommendations have the potential to set the foundation for the successor of the UN Agenda 2030 and the SDGs.

Overview of MERGE engagement with this process: The MERGE team has monitored closely the developments of the HLEG from its inception, using all existing channels and opportunities to share our research outcomes with the members of this group. Some highlights from this engagement include:

- **The inception – The Summit of the Future:** The [Summit of the Future](#) in September 2024 marked a key milestone for this agenda, as it formally launched the HLEG. On this occasion, ZOE Institute represented the MERGE consortium in New York. At a side event titled “Going Beyond GDP: A Multi-Stakeholder Dialogue on Inclusive and Sustainable Development”, co-organised by the Tzu Chi Foundation and the Major Group for Children and Youth, we discussed the dimensions of wellbeing, inclusion, and sustainability that GDP fails to capture, and how alternative metrics can reshape our understanding of prosperity.
- **The development – Consultation on the HLEG interim report and beyond:** After the HLEG published its interim report in November 2025 and started a consultation process, the MERGE consortium worked together to draft a letter with feedback to share with this group. Topics covered in the letter included the conceptual framework, the chosen domains and selection criteria, the proposal to have an adjusted GDP, and issues around implementation and policy uptake (see Annex).

In addition to this, in February 2026 a group of experts that included several MERGE consortium members convened in the JRC premises in Ispra for a workshop on

wellbeing metric measurement and aggregation. As a result of these discussions, a technical brief was sent to the HLEG with further recommendations on reducing the number of indicators in a dashboard, aggregating dashboards to produce indices, measuring SIW efficiency, and global geospatial mapping (see Annex).

Moreover, some individual members of the MERGE consortium were invited to provide specific input on concrete aspects of the HLEG work and their contribution is recognised in the acknowledgment section of the final report.

- **The next steps – Inter-governmental process on Beyond GDP:** In addition to forming the HLEG, the Pact for the Future mandated an inter-governmental process that will essentially shape the real impact of the HLEG recommendations. In order to understand better what this process could look like and how the research community can engage, MERGE co-organised with the United Nations University Centre for Policy Research and WISE Horizons a hybrid expert workshop in April 2026 to exchange ideas on how such a process could support the implementation of the HLEG’s recommendations. The discussions in the context of this workshop are summarised in a policy paper (UNU-CPR, MERGE and WISE HORIZONS, 2026).

Key takeaways:

- **Conceptual convergence on SIW dimensions.** From early on in MERGE project, we have identified that, at a conceptual level, there was a growing convergence around the idea of sustainable and inclusive wellbeing (Rum et al., 2024). This approach has its roots in the Brundtland and Stiglitz reports, and adapted versions have since been implemented by national and supranational organisations, including the European Commission and the OECD. For those working on this field, this concept has provided a positive framing of “Beyond-GDP,” helping the post-growth community to be more coherent and impactful. The HLEG interim report continues in this direction, identifying wellbeing, inclusion and equity, and sustainability as the central and interconnected pillars of its proposed framework for progress, together with a set of foundational principles. Given the important role that narratives play in shaping the foundations for tangible change in technical and policy domains, we see this choice as crucial for maintaining consistent terminology in future developments.
- **SIW connection to future generations and inter-generational fairness.** The Pact for the Future (and the connected initiatives that came before and after) has played an instrumental role in connecting the topics of Beyond GDP and inter-generational fairness. Notably, a sustainable and inclusive wellbeing measuring framework pushes us to recognise the need to preserve the wellbeing of future generations, and

to include this dimension in the way we assess societal progress. At the same time, Beyond GDP indicators can provide a valuable tool when putting an intergenerational fairness approach into practice. All in all, the UN has played an important role in linking these two topics and highlighting the synergies, a step that can be emulated at EU and national level.

- **Science-policy interaction as a way forward.** While the HLEG is primarily comprised by academics, it is worth highlighting that the group paid attention not only to the scientific soundness of their proposal but also to the feasibility of its policy implementation. As a result, their report includes recommendations for multiple stakeholders, including statisticians, national governments, and UN agencies. In this scenario, MERGE work with national statistical institutes staff can provide relevant and experience-based insights for operationalising these recommendations (Abdallah et al., 2025).

4.1.2. The Roadmap for Eradicating Poverty Beyond Growth

Background of the process: In July 2024, Olivier der Schutter, who was at the time Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights presented his report, “Eradicating poverty beyond growth” to the Human Rights Council. In this report, he made the case for shifting away from growth-dependent development strategies and moving towards a human rights economy that places the wellbeing of people and the planet at the centre of economic transformation. Taking this as a starting point and building on consultations with multiple stakeholders, the Roadmap for Eradicating Poverty Beyond Growth, launched in April 2026, aims to provide a comprehensive set of concrete measures to operationalise this shift. The recommendations are structured around five pillars: economic systems transformation; labour market policies and the care economy; universal social protection and essential services; climate, environment and resource management; and trade, finance, debt and global solidarity – underpinned by a transversal focus on governance and participatory democracy.

Overview of MERGE engagement with this process: The MERGE team has actively engaged with this process from the beginning of the project. Some highlights from this collaboration include:

- **The inception – Open consultations and submissions:** While not part of the original project planning, when the opportunity to contribute at early stages to the Roadmap

process emerged, the MERGE consortium prepared a report focused on potential policy instruments to achieve SIW (MERGE Consortium, 2025) and a summary document (see Annex). In this submission, we suggested that the Roadmap outlined a framework that encompasses: i) Technical infrastructure: metrics (e.g. wellbeing indicators), models (e.g. forecasting models), accounts (e.g. System of National Accounts); ii) Governance: policy processes, mechanisms and support structures that enable policy- and decision-making (e.g. policy evaluations); and iii) Policy instruments: concrete policy instruments (e.g. wealth tax). Many of the policy instruments that were included in the MERGE report are to be found in the final version of the roadmap (e.g. wealth tax, job guarantee, universal basic services).

- **The development – Policy profiles:** Following the written submissions, several consortium members were invited to participate in online expert consultations at the end of 2025, and to a closed-door expert session in Geneva in April 2026. Likewise, two MERGE consortium members were invited to draft policy profiles in the area of SIW that are included in the final version of the Roadmap: [Multi-dimensional wellbeing indicators \(policy profile 6.5.\)](#) that capture various aspects of sustainable and inclusive wellbeing, to replace the dominance of the GDP for understanding the state of our economy and society; and [A global accounting system for sustainable and inclusive wellbeing \(policy profile 6.6.\)](#) to replace GDP-centric policy frameworks and realign decision-making with social and ecological outcomes.
- **The next steps – New Economies for Eradicating Poverty and the MERGE Policy Guidelines:** While the mandate of Olivier der Schutter as Special Rapporteur has ended, the work started in the Roadmap will continue through the New Economies for Eradicating Poverty community of practice. The MERGE consortium is committed to continue engaging with it, and one of the avenues of collaboration that we have identified are the MERGE policy guidelines that will complement the Roadmap by reflecting the themes covered in the six pillars but discussing them in European context and in relation to SIW goal.

Key takeaways:

- **Breaking the silos.** The process that surrounded the development of the Roadmap involved a wide array of stakeholders: UN agencies, academics, unions, practitioners, and policymakers – as well as people working on different topics: from debt to health to gender. Creating these connections allowed those involved to understand better how different struggles are connected.

- **Recognising differences.** One of the most interesting features of the Roadmap is the recognition of differences across countries, and the acknowledgment that a shared vision for a better future does not necessarily lead to the same policies everywhere. Through its specific angle on poverty, the Roadmap proposes an ambitious and transformatory pathway that offers meaningful guidance to both the global south and the global north.
- **Care economies as a bridge.** Care emerges in the discussions as a central dimension of people's wellbeing. The concept of care economies provides a fertile ground to change our present living conditions, as it call us to ask questions about how time is allocated across paid and unpaid care work and leisure, about the working conditions of those working in health, education, and domestic work, about how pensions systems are designed among others. Likewise, it also offers a more encompassing perspective related to caring for nature, the planet, the environment and the ecosystem. Nonetheless, these questions do not only hold the potential to create better living conditions under the current economies, but hold the potential to foster true transformation, by changing the way we organise our economic systems.

4.2. Reflections- UN level

This section of the report examines how a SIW approach and metrics can be integrated into UN-level frameworks.

4.2.1 Insights

Metrics need to be connected to governance to have impact: Having the proper technical infrastructure is an important foundation, and the work of the HLEG has been crucial in preparing the groundwork. Nonetheless, its impact and reach will ultimately depend on the inter-governmental process, as this will determine how it is connected with broader governance mechanisms. Notably, the Roadmap already includes technical considerations as part of the governance cross-cutting pillar that sets out the institutional infrastructure needed to support a transformation towards sustainable and inclusive wellbeing.

Linking with policy and finance: For any global Beyond GDP framework to succeed, it must gain traction within policymaking and financial institutions. Given the generally weak enforcement mechanisms, and the broader challenges facing multilateral bodies discussed above, the connection to international financial architecture processes becomes especially important. In this landscape, the work of the [Beyond GDP Global Alliance](#), with its focus on development finance, could become a pivotal bridge between measurement frameworks and real-world policy uptake.

Aligning to avoid fragmentation: The growing number of Beyond GDP initiatives can reinforce one another and help build momentum. Yet this proliferation also carries the risk of fragmentation, with parallel efforts producing disconnected or even competing frameworks, especially given their overlapping timelines. In this context, coordination becomes essential: clarifying the distinct contribution of each initiative while working toward a shared vision and coherent core, including in relation to measurement.

4.2.2 Challenges

Multiple frameworks with a shared vision: Although the Beyond GDP community is increasingly converging around sustainability, inclusion, and wellbeing as core dimensions of societal progress, bringing diverse stakeholders together introduces the challenge of navigating multiple framings. The task is to remain inclusive and sensitive to different contexts while also recognising the strategic value of aligning language and messaging. Achieving coherence without imposing uniformity is essential for maintaining a shared vision across varied constituencies.

Weakened multilateralism and difficulties to increase ambition levels: The rise of the Beyond GDP agenda coincides with a period of heightened geopolitical tensions and a weakened multilateral system. This context can constrain the level of ambition that civil society, statisticians, academics, and even governments are able to bring to negotiations, reducing the political space for bold proposals.

Uncertainties about the post-2030 process: the future of the post-SDG agenda is still uncertain. Most prominently, some of the most important issues relate to the financial crisis that the UN system is currently facing, which might constrain capacities and ambition related to the development of said framework.

Future leadership and priorities: Antonio Guterres, the current UN Secretary-General has been vocal and explicit about the importance of the Beyond GDP agenda, envisioning the work of the UN HLEG as part of his institutional legacy. Nonetheless, as his mandate ends

in 2026, and without clarity at the time of writing the report of who his successor will be, it is difficult to assess the level of importance that this agenda will have in the future, including at the time of the 2025 SDG Summit.

4.2.3 Limitations

Paradigm shift: Similarly to the EU level, the UN realm also shows the need for paradigm change. Interestingly, at the global level time considerations are not so problematic, as often frameworks are designed with the long-term in mind. Nevertheless, the centrality of economic growth that has historically characterised discussions on development and poverty is a structural barrier.

Accountability frameworks: As noted in the insights section, having robust, accurate, and widely available tools to measure the status and progress towards sustainable and inclusive wellbeing is an important first step. Nonetheless, these metrics need to be translated into targets and accompanied by clear and well-defined reporting mechanisms to have real impact.

Balancing universal with local specificity: A persistent challenge that pre-exists and exceeds the Beyond GDP agenda is how to reconcile universal guidance with local specificity. Both processes have acknowledged this tension through offering overarching principles while encouraging adaptation to local contexts. How this balance is ultimately achieved in practice remains an important question for future research considerations.

4.2.4 Learnings

Building broad coalitions: Both processes share the conviction that a Beyond GDP initiative can only advance through broad, multistakeholder engagement. The Roadmap explicitly stresses importance of bringing people living in poverty and actors from the Global South into the discussion. The HLEG, meanwhile, highlights the need to involve statisticians (who will design the technical infrastructure) and national governments, which will ultimately determine the initiative's ambition and scope, from the outset. Building wide-ranging networks across these diverse groups is therefore essential for generating and maintaining momentum behind this agenda.

Connecting the dots: One key strategy for creating the required broad stakeholder engagement, is connecting Beyond GDP to other existing topics, agendas, and institutional

processes. The Roadmap, for instance, seeks alignment with the emerging concept of Human Rights Economy approach, that is gaining traction within the Office of the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights. The HLEG has been connected from the outset to the theme of intergenerational fairness. More broadly, both processes aim to shape discussions on the post-UN Agenda 2030 framework. Positioning Beyond GDP within these wider debates helps strengthen its relevance and visibility.

Building trust: Forming broad coalitions and bringing together stakeholders with diverse backgrounds is fundamentally a trust-building exercise. This groundwork is essential for long-term success. At the same time, it can come into tension with the time-sensitive nature of many of these processes, which often demand rapid turnaround and reaction.

Open process, from beginning to end: In this context, creating space for open consultations in both the HLEG and the Roadmap processes has been an important mechanism for building trust. Such consultations should be standard practice in global initiatives and sustained throughout future developments linked to the Beyond GDP agenda in general and include technical aspects.

5 Conclusion

The discussions across the MERGE engagement activities confirm that the sustainable and inclusive wellbeing approach at the EU level as well as Beyond GDP approach at the UN level have a clear potential to support more coherent, holistic, future-oriented EU and UN policymaking. They can assist building economies that can meet today's multidimensional challenges while safeguarding long-term prosperity and cohesion. However, realising this potential requires a deeper shift in policy paradigms, institutions, and practices.

The discussions showed that a more holistic set of metrics can, in principle, enhance the design, implementation, and monitoring of policies at EU and UN levels, and that existing instruments and processes already offer entry points for mainstreaming this agenda. For example, the EU Budget and its performance framework can benefit from integration of the SIW outcome level metrics to help track the progress of the EU investment. The national and international cases of implementation of wellbeing evidence in budgetary process evidence can serve as a starting point or a guideline. At the same time, while concrete entry points exist in current tools and processes – such as performance, monitoring frameworks, and forthcoming reviews of major EU instruments – persistent data gaps, fragmented

governance, and limited political and institutional buy-in constrain their systematic uptake. Moreover, metrics alone cannot drive transformation. Operational, data, and political hurdles remain significant, particularly in a context where short-term priorities often crowd out longer-term, systemic thinking.

At the UN level, we identified similar patterns and entry points. For instance, the work under the Roadmap evidenced that a beyond GDP approach can be used to support the design and implementation of concrete anti-poverty strategies. Nonetheless, challenges associated with uncertainties for the post 2030 process at the UN level, a weakened multilateral landscape and the multiplicity of initiatives mean, that the momentum behind the agenda also can potentially create a risk of misalignment. This can pose serious challenges that need to be addressed in the future.

The UN- and EU-level engagement overview provided in this report shows different but complementary approaches. There is some potential for both levels albeit differences in context, opportunity windows and stakeholders to be more interconnected. One avenue to explore this can be the intergovernmental process of the implementation of the High-Level Expert Group (HLEG) recommendations.

Finally, we can conclude that advancing MERGE's vision of sustainable and inclusive wellbeing thus emerges as a gradual, iterative and also contested process – one that depends on continued science–policy dialogue, practical demonstrations of added value, linked to citizen's everyday concerns, and sustained efforts to open up institutional space for long-term, futures oriented perspectives.

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ANNEX

EU level

- Presentation materials, concept notes with references and summary documents for EU level events can be accessed here:
<https://mergeproject.eu/event-materials/>
- Documents supporting UN level engagement can be accessed here:
<https://mergeproject.eu/event-materials/>

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Funded by the European Union in the framework of the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement N° 101132524.

This work was funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10092245, 10099476, 10112986].

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation